

WORLD EXPERIENCE OF COMPENSATION PAYMENT AND SOCIAL PROTECTION PAID TO WORKERS AND EMPLOYEES IN CASE OF BODILY INJURY IN THE PROCESS OF WORK AND PRODUCTION

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Annotation

This article provides information on the world experience in compensation and social protection for workers and employees who are injured in the course of work and production, the implementation [of the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the Council Recommendation](#) .

Keywords

non-standard, European Union, transformations, on the platform.

Annotatsiya

mazkur maqolda jahon tajribasida ishchi va xizmatchilarning ish va ishlab chiqarish jarayonida tan jarohati olganda ularga to'lanadigan kompensatsiya to'lovi va ijtimoiy himoyasi, [Ijtimoiy huquqlarning Yevropa ustunini, Kengash tavsiyasini](#) amalga oshirish haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit So'zlar

nostandart, Yevropa Ittifoqi, transformatsiyalar, platformada.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена информация о мировом опыте компенсаций и социальной защиты, выплачиваемых рабочим и служащим при травмах в процессе труда и производства, реализации Европейского столпа социальных прав, рекомендаций Совета.

Ключевые Слова

нестандартный, Евросоюз, трансформации, на платформе.

INTRODUCTION.

Everyone needs social protection at some point in their lives. However, in practice, not all members of society have equal access to it. The rules governing the right to social protection have traditionally been tailored to workers who are full-time, permanently employed by a recognised employer. As a result, people who are self-employed or have non-standard employment relationships may find themselves deprived of adequate social protection.

REFERENCES AND METHODOLOGY.

In the framework of the implementation of [the European Pillar of Social Rights, the Council Recommendation](#) on access to social protection for workers and the self-employed was adopted in November 2019, following [a proposal by the Commission in March 2018. The Impact Assessment Framework developed by the Commission to support the proposal for a Recommendation includes](#) a mapping of access to social protection instruments , an analysis of the impact and impact of extending access to key social protection schemes, and country case studies.

The aim is to support people in non-standard forms of employment and self-employment who are not adequately covered by social insurance programs due to their employment status and are therefore exposed to high economic uncertainty.

The Council Recommendation aims to encourage EU countries to:

- allowing non-standard workers and the self-employed to adhere to social security schemes (closing formal coverage gaps).
- take measures to enable them to build and receive appropriate social benefits as scheme members (effective and adequate coverage) and facilitate the transfer of social security benefits between schemes.
- increasing transparency on social protection systems and rights.

The Recommendation covers social security schemes for unemployment, sickness and health care, maternity or paternity, industrial accidents and occupational diseases, disability and old age.

Within the framework of the Social Protection Committee, the Commission supports Member States and stakeholders in achieving the objectives of the Recommendation.

- through dialogue and mutual learning activities, but also
- by improving statistics and proposing a monitoring system.

was partially updated in [2021](#), [2022](#), and [2023](#).

In January 2023, the Commission published a report to the Council on the implementation of the Recommendation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

, discussed the current social challenges and opportunities of the green transition at the first European Employment and Social Rights Forum, which took place on 16-17 November 2022 .

The cost of living is now the number one concern for people in the European Union. With energy supplies becoming a priority due to the war in Ukraine, people are focusing on paying their bills. If the EU is to meet its climate ambitions, the right policies must be put in place to ensure that the transition is socially fair and brings everyone together.

[of the European Forum on Employment and Social Rights](#), which took place on November 16-17, 2023, was the impact of artificial intelligence on the world of work.

Rapid technological transformations and new digital technologies are creating new jobs, expanding educational opportunities, increasing productivity and improving efficiency. Yet these advances highlight growing inequality and a lack of transparency around the world. Forum speakers discussed how we can ensure fairness, inclusion and transparency as we navigate the new world of work.

Member States were encouraged to implement the principles of the Recommendation and submit a plan of appropriate measures to be taken at the national level by May 15, 2021.

The national plans submitted by Member States during 2021 are listed below. By clicking on each country, you can access the relevant national plan in English and, for some countries, in the national language(s):

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[AUSTRIAN NATIONAL PLAN \(2021\)](#)

This report is Austria's contribution to the implementation of the Council Letter of recommendation dated November 8, 2019

Without prejudice to the competence of Member States to organise their social protection, the Council Recommendation provides the Member States of the European Union with a uniform system of adequate protection that workers and self-employed persons can access formally, effectively and transparently. It is applicable in principle to it.

the following social protection sectors:

- a) Unemployment benefits
- b) sickness and health benefits
- c) Maternity and maternity and equivalent benefits

- d) disability benefits
- e) Old-age and survivor's benefits
- f) Benefits for industrial accidents and occupational diseases

The implementation of the recommendation should be continuously reviewed through the monitoring system (i.e. monitoring report) established by Social Protection.

BULGARIAN NATIONAL PLAN (2021)

The Republic of Bulgaria has provided an updated detailed analysis of the Council text

We would like to emphasize that, as a result of the Recommendation "On the use of social protection for workers and individual entrepreneurs" of November 8, 2019 (hereinafter referred to as the "Recommendation"),

following: under paragraph 19. Member States are encouraged to implement the principles set out in this document

Measures to be taken at the national level until May 15, 2021.

One of the main objectives of the Recommendation is to support all individual entrepreneurs and persons employed in non-standard employment by type of contract or status in relation to all branches of social security where social protection schemes for the population in the labor market are not sufficiently protected.

In this regard, we would like to emphasize that Bulgarian legislation, and in particular the Social Insurance Code (hereinafter referred to as the "SIC"), regulates a very wide range of insured persons.

individuals. All of these are individuals engaged in economic activities (employees and individual entrepreneurs).

persons) on a legal basis. The scope of compulsory insured persons under all social insurance risks includes all workers and employees, regardless of the nature of their work, method of work. sources of payment and financing, including non-standard workers (workers and employees under fixed-term employment relationships, part-time employees under additional or second employment contracts, etc.). All of them are insured against general illness, maternity, disability due to general illness, old age and death, accidents at work and occupational diseases, and unemployment.

ESTONIAN NATIONAL PLAN (2021)

A recent study on platform workers in Estonia concluded:

In 2021, 7% of the population aged 18-64 (about 56,000 people) regularly worked on a platform. For many, platform work is a source of additional income.

Platform work is the only source of income for 4.4% of platform workers (about 2,500 people), and this share

No increase compared to 2018.

Those who worked on the platform over the past year (20.2% of the working-age population, or about 160,000 people) receive an average of 18.4% of their monthly net income from doing business on the platform. At least half of the income is 18.7% for ordinary workers working on the platform (about 10,500 people).

REFERENCES

1. 1999. "The implications of labor market restructuring in industrialized societies for occupational health and safety", in *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, Vol. 20, No. 3.
2. 2004. "Occupational exposure and health problems in small-scale industrial workers in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: A situation analysis", in *Occupational Medicine*, Vol. 54, No. 1.
3. Rosenstock, L.; Cullen, M.; Fingerhut, M. 2006. "Occupational health", in D. Jamison et al. (eds.), *Disease control priorities in developing countries* (2nd ed.). Washington, DC, World Bank.
4. . 2000. *Protecting workers on the periphery* (Development and labor law monograph, No. 1). Cape Town, University of Cape Town – Institute of Development and Labor Law
5. 2012. "The multi stakeholder workshop in Ghana", in *OHS Newsletter*, No. 4, February. (accessed on 13.06.2012).